

A STUDY ON THE OPTIMAL DESIGN OF COMPOSITE ROTOR BLADE CROSS-SECTION USING MICRO GENETIC ALGORITHM

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Keywords: Auto-mesh Generation, Composite Rotor Blade, Design Variable, Micro Genetic Algorithm, Optimal Design, Smearred Properties Method, VABS

ABSTRACT

In this study, the optimal design of composite rotor blade cross-section was carried out to draw design variables for layout design of rotor blade cross-section minimizing blade mass as well as meeting various constraints in the initial design stage of rotor blade. μ -GA known as the effective optimization tool in searching for global optimum or near global optimum was used. Auto-mesh generation program was developed to enable the iterative finite element modeling of blade cross-section if chord profile data of user input and design variables generated by μ -GA were entered. VABS was introduced to calculate stress analysis of cross-section and sectional properties such as mass center, shear center, and equivalent stiffness. Smearred properties method was adopted to simplify mechanical properties of laminate and speed up calculation. Minimum mass of rotor blade was defined as an object function, and design variables such as the thickness and layup angles of a skin, and the thickness, position and width of a torsion box were adopted to optimize composite rotor blade cross-section. Stress failure index, mass center, shear center, equivalent stiffness, blade minimum mass per unit length, and fatigue were chosen as constraints to reflect various design constraints of the real world. Finally, design variables determined through this study can be utilized as input data at the next critical design stage of rotor blade.

1 INTRODUCTION

The optimal design of rotor blade is hierarchically decomposed into upper level optimal problem and lower level optimal problem [1-2]. Upper level optimal problem mainly deals with optimization to enhance performance of aeroelasticity, aeroacoustic noise, and stiffness for rotor blade. In lower level optimal problem, layout, lamination, and material distribution of rotor blade cross-section are optimized to satisfy target values, which are determined from upper level optimal problem, such as target stiffness, blade mass and so on.

In early design stage of rotor blade development, reasonable layout design is requested to determine the structural sizing of rotor blade cross-section such as skin, spar, torsion box and so forth. Therefore the optimal design of composite rotor blade cross-section is carried out to draw design variables for layout design of rotor blade cross-section minimizing objective function as well as meeting various constraints in the initial design stage of rotor blade.

An in-house integrated program for the optimal design of composite rotor blade cross-section developed through this study is to design the optimized blade cross-section satisfying the given design loads, boundary conditions, and constraints at the arbitrary position of rotor blade.

2 COMPOSITION OF OPTIMAL DESIGN PROGRAM

To enable the iterative finite element modeling of blade cross-section automatically during optimization, an in-house code or commercial code to perform auto-mesh of rotor blade cross-section must be reflected in integrated program for the optimal design of composite rotor blade cross-section. Therefore, an in-house type of auto-mesh generation program reflected in this study, based on empirical and mathematical foundation, is capable of executing the automatic finite element modeling of blade cross-section iteratively if chord profile data of rotor blade by user input and design variables generated by μ -GA are entered. Figure 1 shows auto-mesh generation procedure of blade cross-section developed at this study [1].

Figure 1. Auto-mesh generation procedure.

μ -GA known as the effective optimization tool in searching for global optimum or near global optimum is used to investigate the design variables of blade cross-section and evaluate the objective function. Although there are various optimization tools such as particle swarm optimization, traditional genetic algorithms and commercial optimization tool, μ -GA has still much advantages in performing optimization [3].

Figure 2. Smeared properties method

Smeared properties method, which each element of cross-section composed of various layered composites is assumed to be one material with equivalent stiffness, is adopted to simplify mechanical properties of each element. Therefore overall CPU time during optimization can be decreased greatly by simplifying mechanical properties and speeding up calculation. General concept of smeared properties method considered in this paper is seen at figure 2.

VABS is introduced to calculate finite element analysis of cross-section and sectional properties such as mass center, shear center, and equivalent stiffness. As shown in many papers related to VABS,

VABS is very powerful and efficient commercial beam analysis code in calculation of sectional properties and FEA of cross-section [2, 4]. Figure 3 shows the overall beam analysis procedure of VABS [4].

Figure 3. VABS analysis procedure

As aforesaid, an in-house integrated program to optimize composite rotor blade cross-section is composed of each module reflected auto-mesh generation, μ -GA, smeared properties method, and VABS and so on. An analysis flow of optimal design for an in-house integrated program is shown in figure 4 [1].

Figure 4. Analysis flow of optimal design

3 DEFINITION OF OPTIMAL DESIGN CONFIGURATION

Rotor blade mass is always the one of main interests in design of rotor blade. It is very important to design the rotor blade minimizing blade mass as well as satisfying various constraints during optimization. Thus, rotor blade mass is defined as objective function in this study.

Design variables such as the thickness and layup angles of a skin, and the thickness, position and width of a torsion box can be adopted to optimize composite rotor blade cross-section as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5. Design variables of rotor blade cross-section

During optimization, various constraints such as stress failure index, mass center, shear center, equivalent stiffness, blade minimum mass per unit length, and fatigue can be chosen to reflect design constraints of the real world. Rough configuration of rotor blade including cross-section is shown at figure 6.

Figure 6. Configuration of rotor blade

4 NUMERICAL EXAMPLE AND RESULT

As shown at table 1, numerical example is introduced to verify the performance of an in-house integrated program developed for the optimal design of composite rotor blade cross-section. Table 1 consists of 3 cases. Design variables are defined as skin thickness(t_1), tension box thickness(t_2), tension box position(t_3), tension box width(t_4).

	Case 0	Case 1	Case 2
No. of design variable	Analysis using user input	4 (t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4)	
Popsizes		5	10
No. of generation		1,000	
Parameter		Pc = 0.5	

Table 1. Numerical example

Case 0 is the analysis which user input as design variable is adopted, not performing optimal design. User input values of case 0 is shown at table 3. The result of case 0 is compared to optimal design results of case 1 and case 2. The difference between case 1 and case 2 is the number of popsizes in μ -GA. According to the related reference [5-6], in case of using μ -GA as optimization tool, it is

recommended that the adequate popsize of μ -GA is mid-sized population (9 ~ 15). Objective function, design variables and constraints for numerical example are as follows

Definition		Value, Range
Objective function		Rotor blade mass (kg)
Design variable	Skin thickness	$0.25 \text{ mm} \leq t_1 \leq 3.0 \text{ mm}$
	Torsion box thickness	$0.25 \text{ mm} \leq t_2 \leq 3.5 \text{ mm}$
	Torsion box position	$50 \text{ mm} \leq t_3 \leq 100 \text{ mm}$
	Torsion box width	$80 \text{ mm} \leq t_4 \leq 200 \text{ mm}$
Constraints	Strength	Failure index $FI_i < 1, i = 1 \sim 5$
	Characteristic location	Mass center $(0.9 \times \text{chord length}/4) \text{ mm} \leq X \leq (1.1 \times \text{chord length}/4) \text{ mm}$
	Mass	Min. mass per unit length $0.01 \text{ kg/mm} \leq M$

Table 2. Definition of objective function, design variables, constraints

Results of optimal designs for numerical example are summarized at table 3. As the number of generation is increased, mass of case 1 and case 2 are reduced throughout optimal design using integrated program. The difference of optimized rotor blade mass for case 1 and case 2 is about 6.6kg. In case of case 2, although twice times are taken in CPU time as shown at table 3, mass of rotor blade cross-section is more optimized than that of case 1.

	Mass	Skin thickness	Torsion box thickness	Torsion box position	Torsion box width	CPTU time
Case 0	94.13 kg	3.0 mm	3.5 mm	80.0 mm	120.0 mm	-
Case 1	86.9 kg	1.29 mm	2.69 mm	88.3 mm	187.9 mm	56 M
Case 2	80.3 kg	1.11 mm	3.35 mm	76.6 mm	200 mm	120 M

Table 3. Results of optimal design

Definition			Case 0	Case 1	Case 2
Failure index	Skin	G(1)	-0.83	-0.78	-0.70
	Torsion box	G(2)	-0.56	-0.68	-0.79
	Spar	G(3)	-0.93	-0.96	-0.95
	Foam	G(4)	-0.99	-0.99	-0.99
	Honeycomb	G(5)	1.60	-0.59×10^{-4}	-0.91×10^{-3}
Mass center	Lower limit	G(6)	-0.19	-0.14×10^{-3}	-0.02
	Upper limit	G(7)	0.76×10^{-2}	-0.18	-0.17
Mass	Min. mass Per unit length	G(8)	-0.25	-0.18	-0.12

Table 4. Results of non-dimensional constraints

The results of non-dimensional constraint for the last generation number of each case are shown at table 4. From table 4, we can see that all of constraints are satisfied and within range between lower and upper limit of constraints.

Figure 7. Generation no. vs. rotor blade mass

Figure 7 shows the history of generation number vs. rotor blade mass for case 2. As optimization is iteratively performed, an in-house integrated program for the optimal design of composite rotor blade cross-section works well and the converged mass is obtained after about 530 generation number.

Figure 8. Comparison of detailed configuration

Figure 8 shows the detailed configuration of optimal design result for case 2 and compared with that of rotor blade cross-section for case 0. When taken as a whole, thickness of skin and torsion box for case 2 are thin relatively in comparison with case 0 and torsion box width of case 2 is larger than case 0 and spar for case 2 is also slightly smaller than case 0.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the optimal design of composite rotor blade cross-section was carried out to draw design variables for layout design of rotor blade cross-section using integrated program based on μ -GA, auto-mesh generation method, smeared properties method, VABS and so on. Results of numerical example show the possibility that integrated program of this study can be adopted in executing optimal design of composite rotor blade cross-section. Although the adopted numerical example was limited in the number of design variable and constraints, an in-house integrated program of this study can reflect a lot of design variables such as layup angles of composites as well as various constraints including shear center, equivalent stiffness, fatigue and so forth [1].

Design variables determined through this study can be utilized as input data at the next critical design stage of rotor blade.

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